

A Study on Fracture Mechanism of Unidirectional Fibrous Composites

S. Y. Zhang

Institute of Mechanics, Academia Sinica, Beijing, China

ABSTRACT

An analysis on fracture mechanism of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy is presented. The FEM calculations were carried out for stress distribution in the specimen with a mode-I notch; based on the calculated results, a fracture mechanics analysis was given. A new parameter K_{IS} , which characterizes the fracture feature and is named as splitting stress intensity factor, was proposed and the shear fracture characteristic dimension was calculated. Finally, the following conclusions were drawn: The shear strength of the matrix (or the interface) governs the splitting strength of the composites and the shear fracture toughness of the matrix (or the interface) determines the splitting fracture toughness of the composites. The critical splitting stress intensity factor and the shear fracture characteristic dimension are two meaningful parameters of this kind of materials.

INTRODUCTION

Fibrous composites differ from metals in two characteristics: anisotropy and heterogeneity, which render remarkable influence on their fracture behavior. Some investigations on fracture mechanism of fibrous composites have been done (1,2). Tirosh(3), using the J-integral approach, estimated the length of splitting crack in unidirectionally reinforced glass fibre-epoxy. The expression of half-length of the crack was shown to be:

$$R_p = A(\sigma/\tau_0)^2 C \quad (1)$$

where A is a constant depending on elastic constants of material and τ_0 is matrix shear strength. In a recent paper of Mar and Lin(4), the characterization of splitting process in graphite-epoxy composite was described and an estimate of shear fracture toughness of epoxy is given. Based on a number of experimental data, using fracture mechanics analysis and strength analysis, Caprino(5) indicated that there is a characteristic dimension in composites. Recently, Xian(6) has also studied the fracture behavior of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy by tensile testing with notched specimens. The comparison of the tested results of Refs.(5) and (6) is given in Fig.1. Because the component materials are different, two different ordinates are used in Fig.1.

The present paper consists of two parts. At first, the stress field in the neighborhood of the notch of the single edge notched specimen was calculated with FEM. Based on the results of FEM calculations and the related data in Fig.1, a fracture mechanics analysis was made. Then, the new parameter K_{IS} , which characterizes the splitting behavior of fibrous composites and is named splitting stress intensity factor, was proposed and the shear fracture characteristic dimension was estimated.

FINITE ELEMENT COMPUTATIONS

The specimen, of which the stress distribution was calculated, is shown in Fig.2. It is from Ref.(6). Its tested results are indicated by sign \ominus in Fig.1.

Formulation

The hybrid element formulas for plane stress of orthotropic body was used. The derivation of the stiffness matrix and stress matrix is similar to that given in Ref.(7) for isotropic materials.

Element Mesh Pattern

Using the symmetry condition, and separating the specimen through the notch central line, one half of the specimen was calculated. The mesh pattern was shown in Fig.3. The smallest mesh at the root of the notch is $0.1 \times 0.1 \text{ mm}^2$.

Material Models

Three models of materials were calculated. They are as follows:

Isotropic Material Model. The elastic constants are: $E = 2.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Mpa}$, $\nu = 0.3$.

Homogeneous Orthotropic Model. The elastic constants are: $E_L = 106410 \text{ Mpa}$, $E_T = 6059 \text{ Mpa}$, $G_{LT} = 4215 \text{ Mpa}$, $\nu_{21} = 0.016$, $\nu_{12} = 0.28$.

Heterogeneous Orthotropic Model. It is assumed that in the remote part of the specimen from the notch root, the material behaves like the homogeneous body and its elastic moduli are as given above, but in the local region near the notch root its heterogeneity must be taken into consideration. The 54 elements shown by shade lines in Fig.3 are heterogeneous elements, which have elastic properties of fibre and matrix respectively, according to the leaning directions of the shade lines. This model is similar to the local heterogeneous region (LHR) model mentioned in Ref.(10). The elastic constants of carbon fibre and epoxy were given in Ref.(8).

The elastic constants of carbon fibre are: $E_{11} = 229180 \text{ Mpa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.2$, $E_{22} = 14060 \text{ Mpa}$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 14060 \text{ Mpa}$, $G_{23} = 5624 \text{ Mpa}$, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.25$

The elastic constants of epoxy are: $E_{11} = E_{22} = E_{33} = 5483 \text{ Mpa}$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.35$

Loading Conditions

Two kinds of loading conditions were used in the calculations, i. e. the uniform traction condition and the uniform displacement condition. The situation of the tensile tests seems to be the case between them.

Results and discussion

In Fig.4 through Fig.7 and Tables 1a and 1b are the main results. Analyzing these data, the following points can be shown.

1. The curves of $\bar{\sigma}_x$ and $\bar{\sigma}_y$ of homogeneous model in Figs.4 and 5 are similar to the corresponding curves in Ref.(2). The $\bar{\sigma}_x$ curve of heterogeneous model in the region near the notch has wave-like pattern, this is due to the non-homogeneity of the material; but the $\bar{\sigma}_y$ curve of the same material model

has not such wave, this approximating to the uniform normal stress assumption for unidirectional tensile test. In Figs. 6 and 7, both σ_y and σ_{xy} curves of heterogeneous model have a discontinuity at the margin of the local heterogeneous region.

2. Comparing the results of three models under the uniform traction condition, we can see that the value of σ_y of homogeneous orthotropic model is larger than that of isotropic model; this is in agreement with Ref.(2). The stress concentration factor of σ_y in composites is larger than the one in metals. However the σ_y of heterogeneous model is smaller than that of homogeneous model. As to σ_{xy} curve in Fig.7, its value of heterogeneous model is larger than those of both of the isotropic and homogeneous orthotropic models. These comparisons are also listed in Table 1a. These phenomena show that owing to ignorance of non-homogeneity, the homogeneous model under-evaluates the shear stress concentration at the root of notch and under-estimates the possibility for splitting along the fibres.

3. For comparing the results of same material model under two different loading conditions, the curves of σ_x and σ_y along OF under the two loading conditions of homogeneous model are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5, and the results of σ_y and σ_{xy} along OE of heterogeneous model in Figs.6 and 7. Analyzing these curves, it is found that all the three pairs of curves of σ_y and σ_{xy} along OE and the σ_x curve along OF have the same tendency, that is, all those curves under uniform traction condition are higher than those under uniform displacement condition. However as to σ_y along the notch central line OF, in the part near the notch, its value under uniform traction condition is larger than that under uniform displacement condition, but in the part far from notch, the thing is opposite. The reason is the integral of σ_y along OF must equal to the total external traction.

4. The curves of $\sigma_y \sim r^{-1/2}$ and $\sigma_{xy} \sim r^{-1/2}$ are fitted in Fig.5 and Fig.7. It is clear that these two curves are closed to the σ_y and σ_{xy} curves of homogeneous orthotropic model. Because the notch width of the specimen calculated here is very small, the stress field in the vicinity of the notch root practically has the $r^{-1/2}$ singularity. It suggests us that the results be analyzed by using fracture mechanics theory.

FRACTURE MECHANICS ANALYSIS

The Condition of the Initiation and Extension Direction of Cracks

The crack of mode-I in isotropic materials always propagates in self-similar fashion and the extension of it was caused by the normal stress σ_y . However the cracking behavior of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy is quite different. The crack often initiates and propagates in fibre direction from the root of notch. The condition, which governs the initiation and extension direction of crack, can be expressed as follows:

$$G_y / G_x > R_y / R_x \quad (2)$$

where G_x and G_y are energy release rates in directions of x and y respectively, R_x and R_y are the crack propagation resistances. If equation (2) is satisfied, cracking will happen along y direction. This is the very case of the present paper.

The Stress Field in the Vicinity of Crack and the Splitting Stress Intensity Factor

The anisotropic fracture mechanics has developed the expressions of stress in the region near the crack tip. In the present investigation, the crack develops in y direction caused by shear stress σ_{xy} , so we will focus our attention to the expression of σ_{xy} .

$$\sigma_{xy} = \frac{K_{IS}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left[(\cos\theta + \mu_1 \sin\theta)^{-1/2} - (\cos\theta + \mu_2 \sin\theta)^{-1/2} \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

where r is the radius vector and θ is argument as shown in Fig.8. K_{Isc} is the splitting stress intensity factor, the subscript I refers to opening mode-I of crack and s refers to splitting. μ_1 and μ_2 are the two distinct complex roots of the following equation and will always occur in conjugate pairs.

$$\beta_{11}\mu^4 - 2\beta_{16}\mu^3 + (2\beta_{12} + \beta_{66})\mu^2 - 2\beta_{26}\mu + \beta_{22} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where β_{ij} are the components of the compliance matrix, as shown in the following Hook's law:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [\beta_{ij}]\{\sigma\} \quad (5)$$

Substituting values of material constants of homogeneous orthotropic model into equation (4), two distinct imaginary roots can easily be found. Letting θ be equal to $\pi/2$, the simple expression of $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ was obtained.

$$\bar{\sigma}_{xy} = 0.46 K_{Isc} / \sqrt{2\pi r} \quad (6)$$

Making use of the curve of $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ of homogeneous orthotropic model in Fig.7 and the tested results shown in Fig.1, equation (6) gives an estimate of the critical splitting stress intensity factor K_{Isc}

$$K_{Isc} = 83.33 \text{ MN}/\text{M}^{3/2} \quad (7)$$

As compared with the results obtained above, it can also be calculated from the formula given in Ref.(10):

$$K_{Ic} = \sqrt{\pi a} \cdot Y \cdot H \quad (8)$$

where H is a modification factor for anisotropic materials and Y is a modification factor for specimens having finite dimension. Making use of value of H given in Ref.(10) and the formula of Y in (11), it was found that

$$K_{Ic} = 124.8 \text{ MN}/\text{M}^{3/2} \quad (9)$$

An Estimate of Fracture Characteristic Dimension

In Ref.(5) an idea of fracture characteristic dimension was mentioned. When the average stress within a definite region reaches the failure strength, the material will rupture. The size of this region is called fracture characteristic dimension and noted by r_c .

Based on the idea stated above, the splitting fracture characteristic dimension at the tip of crack of mode-I can be estimated as follows: The distribution of shear stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ along OE in equation (6) is shown in Fig.9. According to the failure criterion afore-mentioned, the following formula is given

$$r_c \bar{\sigma}_{xy} = \int_0^{r_c} \bar{\sigma}_{xy} dr = \int_0^{r_c} 0.46 K_{Isc} / \sqrt{2\pi r} \cdot dr \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ is the shear strength of composites. Integrating (10) leads to

$$r_c = 0.135 (K_{Isc} / \bar{\sigma}_{xy})^2 = B (\bar{\sigma}_b / \bar{\sigma}_{xy})^2 a \quad (11)$$

This formula is similar to formula (1). In fact, these formulas have similar physical meaning.

Thus, if $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ is known, making use of formula (11), the r_c can be obtained. Here the $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ interlaminar shear strengths of two kinds of composites, both of which have epoxy as matrix, are used as epoxy shear strength in the following calculations. Refs. (11) and (12) provide two sets of tested data. It was seen that, although the materials of the fibres and their volume fraction are different from each other, the shear strengths are nearly the same. So the conclusion might be deduced that the shear fracture of the matrix

governs the interlaminar shear strength of the composites. The average value of the epoxy shear strength we derived from the two papers is 39.1 Mpa.

It is also known that the ratio of the shear stress in the matrix to the shear stress in composite is equal to the ratio of elastic modulus of the matrix to that of the composite (4). i.e.

$$\tau_m / \bar{\sigma}_{xy} = E_m / E_c \quad (12)$$

where τ_m is shear strength of epoxy. Thus

$$\bar{\sigma}_{xy} = 39.1 E_c / E_m \quad (13)$$

Substituting (13) into (11), we obtained

$$r_c = 0.135 (K_{Isc} / 39.1 \times E_m / E_c)^2 \quad (14)$$

Making use of value of (7) and the values of E_c and E_m , we obtained

$$r_c = 1.66 \text{ mm} \quad (15)$$

This value is comparable with the results obtained in Ref.(5).

Shear Fracture Toughness of Epoxy

Having obtained the characteristic dimension r_c and the shear strength of epoxy τ_m , the shear fracture toughness of epoxy may be evaluated from the following formula:

$$K_s = \tau_m / \sqrt{\pi r_c} \quad (16)$$

This means that if there is no man-made notch or the inherent imperfection is smaller than r_c , the material will have the strength τ_m . But when the imperfection or discontinuity is larger than r_c , the shear strength will decrease saliently due to the stress concentration. At this time the fracture toughness can be given by the following formula:

$$K_s = \tau_m \sqrt{\pi (a + r_c)} \quad (17)$$

Inserting the values of r_c and τ_m into (16), we obtained

$$K_s = 2.8 \text{ MN}/\text{M}^{3/2} \quad (18)$$

For the sake of comparison, the fracture toughness can also be calculated from the fracture surface energy of epoxy. It was known that the fracture surface energy $\gamma = 300 \text{ J}/\text{M}^2$; and that the relationship between stress intensity factor and fracture surface energy is

$$K_s^2 = G E = 2 \gamma E \quad (19)$$

then, the critical fracture toughness was obtained

$$K_s = 1.9 \text{ MN}/\text{M}^{3/2} \quad (20)$$

This result is comparable with that of (19). The value estimated in Ref. (4) is much smaller.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The shear stress at the root of notch calculated for homogeneous orthotropic model is smaller than that for heterogeneous model, this indicates that owing to ignorance of non-homogeneity, the shear stress near the notch was under-estimated and so the possibility of splitting was under-estimated.

2. The fracture of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite

with opening mode notch under tensile load was caused by shear stress. The shear strength of matrix (or interface) dominates the splitting strength and the fracture toughness of matrix (or interface) determines the fracture toughness of the composite in splitting.

3. The critical splitting stress intensity factor proposed in the present paper is a significant material parameter, and the characteristic dimension is also a meaningful material parameter. Both the two parameters characterize the ability of the material to resist the splitting failure. The larger their values are, the better the allowance of damage in the material is.

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Table 1a Calculated results of the present paper

homogeneous model				isotropic model				heterogeneous model			
max. average stress of ele.		ratio		max. average stress of ele.		ratio		max. average stress of ele.		ratio	
σ_y	10.83	σ_y/σ_x	17.9	σ_y	7.14	σ_y/σ_x	4.30	σ_y	5.59	σ_y/σ_x	8.38
σ_x	0.606	σ_x/σ_{xy}	0.63	σ_x	1.66	σ_x/σ_{xy}	0.98	σ_x	0.67	σ_x/σ_{xy}	0.34
σ_{xy}	0.965	σ_y/σ_{xy}	11.2	σ_{xy}	1.65	σ_y/σ_{xy}	4.22	σ_{xy}	1.94	σ_y/σ_{xy}	2.87

Table 1b Calculated results of Ref. (2) $\sqrt{\frac{F}{a}} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\infty}}$

homogeneous model				isotropic model			
max. average stress of ele.		ratio		max. average stress of ele.		ratio	
σ_y	6.30	σ_y/σ_x	48.1	σ_y	2.00	σ_y/σ_x	5.26
σ_x	0.13	σ_x/σ_{xy}	0.23	σ_x	0.38	σ_x/σ_{xy}	0.64
σ_{xy}	0.57	σ_y/σ_{xy}	11.1	σ_{xy}	0.59	σ_y/σ_{xy}	3.38

Fig. 2 Configuration of specimen

N.B. ρ and a are radius and half length of major axis

Fig. 1 Reduction of strength with notch length

Fig. 3 Finite element mesh

Fig. 8 Coordinate of formula (8)

Fig. 9 σ_{xy} distribution near the notch

Fig. 4 σ_x distribution along notch central line OF

Fig. 5 σ_y distribution along notch central line OF

Fig. 6 τ_{xy} distribution along OE (normal to the root of notch)

Fig. 7 σ_{xy} distribution along OE (normal to the root of notch)